

The last 18 months have seen some hectic activity in forest nursery developments throughout Australia. Changes in the legislation affecting tree farm investments came too late last year for many in the industry to respond to straight away, but initial estimates look very promising for some major expansions at forest nurseries.

Warrick Nelson,
Marketing Manager
Transplant Systems

For our part, we have been involved in many of these forest nursery developments. Probably the biggest has been the new North Forests nursery, but other activities have kept us very busy.

Two years ago at the Australian Forest Growers Conference in Mt Gambier, I was told how wonderfully seedlings from Lannen side slot containers performed compared to bare root or non-pruning containerised stock. The proof of the pudding is certainly in the eating - in our case the adoption of Lannen side slot trays by many of the major forestry companies in Australia and around the world.

I look forward to participating even more in this exciting time in Australian forestry. We have some great products, you have great ideals - together we can do our bit to achieving the 2020 Vision.

New size Pottiputki

The popular Pottiputki planting tube is now even better. The 5.5 size, specifically developed to better suit seedlings grown in Lannen Plantek 81F seedling trays is now available from Transplant Systems, Melbourne or Perth.

The four sizes now available are the number 5, internal diameter of 49mm and suggested for Lannen 121F cells, the new number 5.5, i.d. of 53mm and suggested for Lannen 63F and 81F cells, number 6 with i.d. of 61mm suggested for larger cells such as the Lannen 64F trays. The largest Pottiputki is number 7 with an i.d. of 68mm for even larger plants.

Pottiputki planting tubes are available in Australia through many regional outlets, or contact Transplant Systems directly in Melbourne or Perth (see bottom of page 2 for contact details).

North Forests' New Nursery

Six months down the track is a good time to assess the results of a new forest seedling nursery. At eight million capacity, the new North Forests' nursery at Somerset, Tasmania, is a clear indication of North's direction in the timber industry. The nursery is designed to grow *Eucalyptus* seedlings using seed from the North's breeding programme.

Design and construction of the nursery was on a turn-key basis. Transplant Systems won the tender in a joint venture with Fluor Daniel, project managers. The nursery includes a complete in-line mixing, filling and high-speed

The first batch of healthy seedlings nearly ready for despatch. Lannen side slot trays have been specified to take advantage of the root-pruning on the sides of the cell walls. Rolling benches are used throughout the nursery.

The first crop of *Eucalyptus* seedlings germinating in the fully climate-controlled glasshouse. Note the uniform filling of the trays, particularly on the edges. Inset: *Eucalyptus* seed just germinating.

sowing line; automated travelling irrigation booms and many features to be expected in a modern nursery.

Transplant Systems were pleased to be able to supply and install many of the machines critical to the success of the new nursery. A Gleason Batch Mixer is the starting point of the sowing cycle. These robust machines are well proven in Australian nurseries. The specific design of the agitation rotors ensures an even and thorough mixing within the normal 3-5 minute mixing cycle.

The Lannen FL-2 filling machine incorporates excellent substrate handling components to ensure an even filling and compaction in all cells of the trays. A vibrator assembly, dual tamping brushes and spreader blades assist in achieving the excellent filling result crucial to ensuring uniform growth of seedlings. The associated automatic storage hopper keeps a ready supply of mixed substrate for continuous filling.

Lannen side-slot tray technology was chosen. The side slots and internal cell architecture are specifically designed to eliminate root spiralling, create a fine, fibrous root system to recreate a natural root form after planting, and

Lannen irrigation booms being tested for evenness and accuracy of their spray pattern during installation. Each gantry can water or spray more than 1.5 million seedlings. Fungicide is introduced by means of an in-line injector. This saves time and reduces staff exposure to chemicals.

retain the ease of handling and economies of a containerised propagation system. The trays are automatically de-stacked into the filling machine.

A Hamilton Drum Seeder is used to sow the cleaned and graded Eucalypt seed into the cells. Precision in excess of 98% accuracy during routine sowing operations is readily achieved with this Drum Seeder.

Once in the growing areas, the seedlings are watered and fertilised using greenhouse booms from ITS, and outdoor booms from Lannen. These booms incorporate a range of automated functions, but are also capable of being controlled by the computerised climate control system.

North Forests have demonstrated what can be achieved by adopting a systems approach to nursery design and operation. We at Transplant Systems are pleased that we could contribute our skills and top-quality products from specialist nursery equipment manufacturers towards the obvious success of this nursery.

DPI Queensland on the move

Lannen irrigation booms have been installed at the completely revamped Beerburum Nursery, north of Brisbane. Containerised pine cuttings are the main crop in this nursery, with the automatic irrigation booms playing a major role in keeping the cuttings evenly moist during the critical rooting stage

Lannen outdoor irrigation booms at DPI, Beerburum nursery. These booms are also used for applying fungicides to the crop.

Bunnings pines in 63F

Bunnings Treefarms have recently begun growing their *Pinus radiata* seedlings in Lannen 63F containers. The desired size specification is between 15 and 20 cm tall, greater than 3mm collar diameter and a well-consolidated root plug for ease of handling and planting. Planting is done during the normal winter wet season using Pottiputki planting tubes, planting into weed-free, prepared ground.

Simon Hunter, nursery manager for Bunnings Treefarms, WA, with a radiata pine seedling nearly ready for planting. Simon says, "We expect better survival and better early growth. Containerised stock gets away quicker than our bare root stock. We also save on planting costs when using containerised plants."

Lannen side slot trays are designed with the biological needs of the tree in mind. Note the root guiding angles to actively direct roots to the air-pruning side

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